

ENHANCING UTILIZATION OF FINGER MILLET AS AN ALTERNATIVE CEREAL CROP IN SUB SAHARAN AFRICA

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Abstract

Finger millet grain (*Eleusine coracana* (L.) Gaertn) is a rich source of nutrients compared to other cereal crops. The crop as a short season is adapted to marginal lands, tolerant to drought and can contribute significantly meeting the food demand for ever increasing population in developing countries. Finger millet has higher nutritional value compared to other cereals and can potentially make higher contribution to food and nutritional security. Finger millet grain however has anti nutritional factors such as phytin and polyphenols that reduce digestibility, palatability and availability of other nutrients. Different forms of grain pre-treatments such as boiling, cooking, roasting and soaking of the grain for specified periods improve the nutritional quality. There is wide diversity of unexploited finger millet genetic resources. This has the potential to contribute towards sustainable agriculture particularly in drought prone and marginal areas of Africa through breeding and selection for improved varieties. This review focuses on key challenges of finger millet production, value addition and processing of the crop as a way to improve adoption and productivity of finger millet in Africa.

Key words: Climate change, *Eleusine coracana*, plant genetic resources, small grain

Introduction

Despite efforts and achievements in the agricultural sector, climate change remains a major challenge in efforts to achieve food and nutritional security. Use of drought tolerant crops contributes towards sustainable food and nutritional security (Gebre,2019). Drought tolerant cereals such as finger millet (requiring 200-500mm rainfall) play a pivotal role in ensuring food security for millions of smallholder farmers in the Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) and other Low- and Middle-income countries (LMIC) (Amadou et al.,2013; Bora, 2013; Gupta et al.,2017).

Finger millet is widely cultivated in arid and semi- arid regions of SSA. It is a small grain cereal crop with recognised centres of diversity in Asia and Africa. There are 10 genera and 20 species described for this crop (Negi et al.,2017). The crop belongs to the family *Graminae* and the common name originated from finger like branching of the panicle which resembles the shape of human fingers. Finger millet is considered ‘nutritious millet’ as the grain is nutritionally better than other cereals like wheat and maize, providing high quantity and quality of proteins, minerals, calcium and vitamins (Kumar et al.,2017). Africa contributes 50-60% of global finger millet production and the major producers are Ethiopia, Kenya, Nigeria, Malawi, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia and Zimbabwe (FAOSTAT,2020).

Adaptation of finger millet in semi-arid tropics of Africa

Finger millet is adapted to wide range of climates and can withstand significant levels of moisture stress a phenomenon common in SSA (Rathore, 2019). It is more drought tolerant and can survive in high temperature environments where other cereals such as maize and wheat cannot grow (Rathore,2019). In semi-arid areas of Africa that are suitable for finger millet production, low precipitation is a common feature (Mathur et al.,2012). A number of acclimatisation mechanisms allow the crop to cope with abiotic factors such as heat stress. At physiological level, ion transporters, osmo-protectants and antioxidants are involved in tolerance of finger millet to heat and drought (NRC,1996). Furthermore, the crop has good pest and disease resistance, high multiplication rate and environmental plasticity (Gari,2002; Apole,2019). For example, the crop can withstand soil salinity and water logging that are phenomena associated with climate change in the SSA. The crop has a long postharvest storability and is tolerant to storage pests that give it an advantage over other crops for smallholder farmers where high post-harvest losses are common (Gupta et al.,2017).

Finger millet production trends in sub-Saharan Africa

Total production of finger millet is estimated at 4.5 to 5 million tonnes worldwide and India is the largest producer at 2.5 million tonnes followed by Africa at 2 million tonnes (FAO,2020). Finger millet ranks fourth in importance after sorghum, pearl millet and fox tail millets in the semi-arid regions of the world (FAOSTAT,2020). Production of finger millet is still grown principally as a subsistence crop with yields ranging from 0.19 – 0.9 t/ha (Table 1) which is low compared to India. In SSA, finger millet is considered an important cereal for many rural communities in East, Central and Southern Africa. Despite its importance towards food and nutritional security, finger millet is largely considered a ‘poor man’s crop’ hence a neglected crop in most developing countries (Gari, 2002).

Table 1. Comparison of area planted and production of finger millet in countries of different regions in Africa and India

Region/Country	Area planted (million ha)	Production (Tonnage, million)	Average yield (t/ha)
India	1.19	1.98	1.66
West Africa	6.24	5.22	0.74
Nigeria	5.10	4.53	0.88
Mali	1.14	0.69	0.60
East Africa	2.45	0.77	0.51
Tanzania	0.22	0.16	0.73
Sudan	1.95	0.54	0.28
Southern Africa	0.39	0.09	0.23
South Africa	0.21	0.04	0.19
Zimbabwe	0.18	0.05	0.27

FAOSTAT, 2020

Role of finger millet to mitigate food insecurity in sub-Saharan Africa

Consumption of finger millet as a food crop in Africa is primarily in the form of thick porridge. The grain is high in amylase enzymes responsible for conversion of starch to sugar and is used for malting and brewing purposes (Obilana and Manyasa, 2002). The straw is useful for livestock feed while husks have a high fibre content that is a valuable poultry feed. The grain is processed into baking flour either on its own or in blend with other grains, making a composite flour that is readily available in supermarkets (Manyasa,2013).

In Zimbabwe and many countries in SSA, maize and wheat form a major part of the food basket, small grains such as finger millet play a minor role in household food security (Rukuni et al.,2006). Maize is grown and consumed as the staple food crop even in drier areas where small grain crops such as finger millet perform better than maize on average. There is a need for crop diversification and reduction of dependence on maize that is dominant source of calories through inclusion of small grain crops in SSA (Mudimu,2003). However, finger millet is considered ideal crop for different food habits and preferences of people due to its nutritional richness (Babu et al.,2013).

Challenges of finger millet production

There are a number of constraints to the production of finger millet in Africa. Among these are abiotic stresses such as low soil fertility, low rainfall that is poorly distributed and high temperature (Krishnamurthy et al.,2016). Soil salinity also affects the growth and yield of finger millet depending on the soil type and soil moisture availability (Yamunarani et al.,2016; Ramakrishnan et al.,2017). Biotic factors that contribute to reduction of finger millet yield are: parasitic weeds *Striga asiatica*, diseases such as downy mildew and fungal blast disease (Kumar and Kumar,2011). Pest infestations which include fall army worm, stink bugs and aphids which are common during rainy season leading to significant yield losses (Orr et al.,2016). Predation by quelea birds during the soft and hard dough stage also contribute to significant losses in finger millet grain yield.

Socio economic challenges and research intervention in finger millet production

Maize production still dominates in SSA compared to small grains because it offers higher yields, requires less labour for bird scaring and processing (Sukume et al.,2000). Low yield potential in finger millet a major obstacle and a setback in the production and adoption process. Lack of remunerative market prices of finger millet which often fails to cover production costs and give reasonable profit margin accelerates crop neglect. This ultimately discourages rainfed finger millet production leading to shift in crop to other high yielding cereals such as maize and wheat (Sakamma et al.,2017). Lack of policies for promoting finger millet production, poor pricing models, poor and inaccessible market channels, lack of loan facilities and prevalence of inefficient traditional processing methods are other constraints. (Mgonja et al., 2017). In other countries, efforts to improve marketing and other cross cutting themes such as germplasm conservation, policies and public awareness were implemented to improve production (Padulosi ,2009; Rodger et al.,2009).

Research interventions to improve production and utilisation of finger millet

Africa has the largest finger millet germplasm collection preserved across various gene banks (Gupta et al., 2017). This presents a good opportunity for crop improvement using the available material. Much effort has been placed on improvement of finger millet for different agro-ecological environments of Africa (Gupta et al.,2017). In Eastern Africa, there is ongoing

research to improve finger millet varieties for traits which include yield; pest and disease tolerance, *Striga asiatica* weed tolerance; adaptation to local environments and speciality attributes to meet market and industrial qualities (Apole,2019). Research activities, however, need to address bottlenecks along finger millet value chain. These range from lack of characterisation and improved varieties: poor knowledge on cultivation practices; availability of good quality seeds and value addition. Research and development efforts should be in line with farmer’s expectations and an integrated approach that facilitates the adoption of appropriate practices needs to be addressed (Groverman et al., 2018). The characteristic traits of high nutritional value and drought tolerance in finger millet make it a researchable crop on genetic architecture and gene expression (Gupta et al.,2017).

In the past 5-10 years, few African countries have released more than five improved finger millet varieties. For example, in Zimbabwe only two varieties namely FMV1 and FMV2 that were released and are found back on the market. In Kenya, only four varieties, P224, Gulu E, KAT/FM1 and Lanet / FM1 were released. In Uganda, five common varieties namely Gulu E, Engecy, Serene, Seremi 1 Seremi 2 and Emoni are available. These variety release figures are considerably lower than those for maize in various countries in SSA. Thus, there is need or more finger millet plant breeding research to develop high yielding and adapted varieties.

Finger millet use, value addition products and marketing

There is a limited range of value-added products from finger millet in most countries in SSA (Verma and Patel, 2013). This limits the demand for the crop, particularly in urban areas where consumers prefer processed value-added products. Enhancement and promotion of finger millet food products can increase demand. Consumption of such food products can improve nutritional status and livelihoods for poor marginalised communities (Sircar et al.,2019). Finger millet can be processed to produce nutritive healthy foods using traditional and improved technology to produce convenient food products (Table 2) (Joel et al.,2005; Ramashia et al.,2019).

Table 2. Value added finger millet products in Asia that are being relevant to SSA

Product	Main ingredients
Composite flour	Finger millet seed (30%) and wheat seed (70%)
Malt-weaning food	Spouted seed components; finger millet seed (70%), green gram (15%) and chick pean (15%)
Finger millet cakes	Finger millet four and wheat
Cookies	Finger millet flour and wheat
Doughnuts	Finger millet flour and wheat

It is important however to be aware that finger millet contains several antinutritional factors that have the ability to reduce bioavailability of nutrients from other food sources such as legumes when consumed together. Phytic acid and tannins are major nutrient inhibitors in finger millet grain. Processing methods can however, be used to reduce anti nutritional factors to permissible amounts. Grain treatments like roasting, soaking, boiling, parboiling,

fermentation, milling, germination, decortications and extrusion cooking reduce tannin content in finger millet (Ramashia et al.,2019).

Way forward and future perspectives

Finger millet is a strategic grain to meet food and nutritional requirement in rural or marginal areas to complement diets in where malnutrition is endemic. There is need for deliberate efforts by African National Agricultural Research Systems and their respective Governments to promote finger millet production as an alternative cereal. Aggressive marketing systems, better producer prices and other incentives by government agencies, if implemented, can stimulate demand, for the crop.

Plant breeding improvements are also feasible given the genetic diversity that exists within the continent. Wild and weed relatives can be harnessed to enhance the genetic potential of the crop in SSA. Presence of landraces that are adapted to certain ecological niches can be a starting point for genetic improvement. Research and development of high yielding varieties especially open pollinated varieties is critical, where resource constrained farmers can retain seed for future cultivation, hence reducing production costs. Mechanisation of processing can further stimulate an uptake of the crop.

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